
MEDICINAL VALUE OF MANGROVES AND ITS ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTIES – A
REVIEW

¹ Piyusha Suresh Shelar, ² Vijay Kumar Reddy. S, ³ Gauri Suresh Shelar and ⁴ G. Vidya Sagar Reddy,
¹ Department of Fisheries Environment, Fisheries College and Research Institute, Thoottukudi, Tamilnadu,
India – 628 008, ² Department of Fish Processing Technology, College of Fisheries, Mangalore, Karnataka,
India – 575 001, ³ Department of Aquaculture, College of Fisheries, Shirgaon, Maharashtra, India – 415
629, ⁴ Department of Fish Processing Technology, College of Fishery Science, Muthukur, Andhra Pradesh,
India.

ABSTRACT

For a long period of time in history mangrove plant extracts have been used for various producing a wide array of novel products. Plant-derived substances have recently become of great interest owing to their versatile applications. Besides its general products, mangroves also provide many non timber products such as tannin, fish poison, medicine, food and fodder. Mangrove and mangrove associates contain biological compounds that are active antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal in nature. They also possess antifeedant, molluscicidal and pesticidal properties. Mangrove plants are a rich source of steroids, triterpenes, saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids and tannins. Extracts from different mangrove plants are reported to possess diverse medicinal properties such as antibacterial and antihelminthics. The medicinal value of mangroves and their antimicrobial properties are discussed in this paper in brief.

KEYWORDS: Mangrove, *Rhizophora*, plant extracts, Antibacterial, Antiviral, Antifungal.

INTRODUCTION

The name 'Mangrove' for this peculiar community originated from a combination of the Portuguese word 'mangue' that stands for tree and an English word 'grove' that stands for a stand of trees. These mangrove tree communities were described as 'mangales' by Walsh and as 'mangals' by Tomlinson (Tomlinson, 1986 and Walsh, 1974). However the term mangrove according to Chapman expresses two distinctly different notions. The first one refers to halophytic species, in a sense it is a botanically diverse, nontaxonomic expression given to include approximately 12 families and more than 50 species of tropical trees and shrubs. Secondly, the term mangrove encompasses the entire intertidal plant community including individual mangrove species (Chapman, 1970). Other synonymous terms suggested include 'tidal forest', 'tidal swamp forest', 'mangrove community', 'mangrove ecosystem', 'mangal' (Macnae, 1968), 'mangrove swamp' and 'coastal woodlands' (Chelliah, 2001).

Mangrove plant extracts have been used for centuries as popular method for treating several health disorders. Plant-derived substances have recently become of great interest owing to their versatile applications. Besides, mangroves also provide many non timber products such as tannin, fish poison, medicine, food and fodder (Bandaranayake, 2002). Mangroves are biochemically unique, producing a wide array of novel natural products. Mangrove and mangrove associates contain biologically active antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal compounds (Bandaranayake, 1998).

Tomlinson recognized three groups of mangroves: major mangrove species, minor mangrove species and mangrove associates (Tomlinson, 1986). The major species are the strict or true mangroves, recognized by most or all of the following features:

1. They occur exclusively in mangal,
2. They play a major role in the structure of the community and have the ability to form pure stands,

3. They have morphological specializations - especially aerial roots and specialized mechanism of gas exchange,
4. They have physiological mechanisms for salt exclusion and/or excretion,
5. They have viviparous reproduction, and
6. They are taxonomically isolated from terrestrial relatives. The strict mangroves are separated from their nearest relatives at least at the generic level, and often at the sub-family or family level.

The minor mangrove species are less conspicuous elements of the vegetation and rarely form pure stands. According to Tomlinson, the major mangroves include 34 species in 9 genera and 5 families (Tomlinson, 1986). The minor species contribute 20 additional species in 11 genera and 11 families for a total of 54 mangrove species in 20 genera and 16 families. Duke on the other hand identified 69 mangrove species belonging to 26 genera in 20 families (Duke, 1992). One family falls in the fern division (Polypodiophyta); the remainder are in the Magnoliophyta (Angiosperms). Families containing only mangroves are the Aegialitiaceae, Avicenniaceae, Nypaceae and Pellicieraceae. Two orders (Myrtales and Rhizophorales) contain 25% of all mangrove families. By reconciling common features from Tomlinson and Duke, we recognize 65 mangrove species in 22 genera and 16 families.

There are a number of problems with mangrove taxonomy and many of these are based on hybridization between described species (Duke, 1992). For instance, the systematic distinction between *Rhizophora mucronata* in Eastern Africa, *R. stylosa* in Australia, and their putative hybrids is unclear. *Rhizophora lamarckii*, which occurs in New Caledonia, Papua New Guinea and Queensland, Australia, is a sterile F1 hybrid between *R. apiculata* and *R. stylosa*. *Rhizophora x annamalayana*, found in a south Indian mangrove forest, was first identified as *R. lamarckii* but has since been reidentified as a new species hybrid between *R. mucronata* and *R. apiculata* (Kathiresan, 1995a).

Some hybrids, like *Rhizophora x harrissoni*, cannot be confirmed with wax chemistry (Dodd, *et al.*, 1995). Molecular analyses may help eventually resolve the taxonomic problems. For example, DNA sequence data from the chloroplast gene *rbcL* indicate that the Rhizophoraceae belongs not to the Myrtales, but to a rosoid clade that includes the families Euphorbiaceae, Humiriaceae and Malpighiaceae (Conti, *et al.*, 1996). Mangrove forests have economical and ecological importance. The mangrove plants are useful for erosion protection and also for marine animals. Several plants are used for medical purposes e.g. *Acanthus ebracteatus* Vahl for chronic wound (Sujampong, 1979), the bark of *Rhizophora apiculata* Blume for diarrhoea and wound (School of Thai traditional medicine, 1981; Traditional Medicine Association, 1980), the bark of *R. mucronata* for diarrhoea (Phongboonrod and Mai, 1976).

Microorganisms especially viruses and bacteria are the major pathogenic organisms have potential to cause human diseases and diseases of aquatic organisms. The antibiotics discovery provided an important tool to combat the diseases of microbial origin. Since umpteen numbers of medicinal plants have been used in folklore medicine for treatment of several bacterial and viral diseases. Emerging viral and bacterial diseases demand the global scientific community to develop antiviral and antibacterial drugs from diverse herbal resources. Hitherto unknown viral and bacterial pathogens and diseases of unknown aetiology have devastated human and animal resources in different parts of the world. Bird flu virus, SAR virus, west Nile virus, Chikungunya virus, WSSV, TSV, YTV, Koi carp herpes virus and Hepatopancreatic parvovirus are some of the striking examples not witnessed earlier. The medicinal value of mangrove plants based on traditional wisdom is being appreciated with proven effect after in depth scientific investigation using modern biotechnological tools (Yaadfone Association, 1981).

A number of mangroves and associates contain poisonous substances, which also show biological activities such as antifungal, antibacterial, antifeedant, molluscicidal and pesticidal properties. Mangrove plants are a rich source of steroids, triterpenes, saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids and tannins. Extracts from different mangrove plants are reported to possess diverse medicinal properties such as antibacterial and antihelminthics.

1. Antimicrobial properties of Mangroves

Mangroves with Antibacterial Properties

Mangrove plant extracts have been used for centuries as a popular method for treating several health disorders. Plant-derived substances have recently become of great interest owing to their versatile applications. Mangroves are biochemically unique, producing a wide array of novel natural products. Mangrove and mangrove associates contain biologically active antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal compounds.

The antibacterial activity of the leaves and bark of mangrove plants, *Avicennia marina*, *A. officinalis*, *Bruguiera sexangula*, *Excoecaria agallocha*, *Lumnitzera racemosa* and *Rhizophora apiculata* was evaluated against antibiotic resistant pathogenic bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Proteus sp.* Soxhlet extracts of petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, ethanol and water were prepared and evaluated the antibacterial activity using agar diffusion method. Most of the plant extracts showed promising antibacterial activity against both bacterial species. However, higher antibacterial activity was observed for *Staphylococcus aureus* than *Proteus sp.* The highest antibacterial activity was shown by ethyl acetate of mature leaf extracts of *E. agallocha* for *Staphylococcus aureus*. All ethyl acetate extracts showed higher inhibition against *S. aureus* while some extracts of chloroform, ethyl acetate and ethanol gave inhibition against *Proteus sp.* None of the petroleum ether and aqueous extracts showed inhibition against *Proteus sp.*

Recently many bioactive and pharmacologically active phytochemicals have been isolated from mangrove plants. For example, *Bruguierols A, B& C* were isolated from *Bruguiera gymnorhiza* which actively inhibit the growth of both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria including mycobacteria and resistant strains @ 12.5 µg/ml concentrations (Han, *et al.*, 2004). FAME (Fatty Acid Methyl Ester) of leaves of *Finlaysonia abovata* and *Excoecaria agallocha* have exhibited the control of *Micrococcus sp.*, *Aeromonas hydrophilla*, *E.coli*, *Vibrio alginolyticus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *B. Pumilus* and *ebisiella pneumoniae* due to the presence of antibacterial activity of fatty acids (Agoramoorthy, *et al.*, 2007 and Mishra *et al.*, 2009). Mangroves are also rich in polyphenols and tannins (Achmadi, *et al.*, 1994; Kathiresan and Ravi, 1990). The levels of these substances may vary seasonally (Basak, *et al.*, 1998), but older data should be interpreted cautiously since standard methods for measuring tannins are very inaccurate for mangrove leaves (Benner, *et al.*, 1990). Substances in mangroves have long been used in folk medicine to treat disease (Bandaranayake, 2002).

Other unique mangrove biochemicals have potential commercial applications (Kathiresan, 2000). For example, mangrove extracts kill larvae of the mosquitoes *Anopheles stephens* (Kathiresan and Thangam, 1987), *Culex tritaeniorhynchus* (Kathiresan and Thangam, 1989), *Aedes aegypti* (Thangam and Kathiresan, 1992a; Thangam and Kathiresan, 1991; Thangam and Kathiresan, 1994) and *Culex quinquefasciatus* (Thangam and Kathiresan, 1997). Phenols and flavonoids in mangrove leaves serve as UV-screening compounds. Hence, mangroves tolerate solar-UV radiation and create a UV-free, under-canopy environment (Moorthy, 1995). These substances also contribute to a black tea that can be extracted from mangrove leaves (Kathiresan, 1995b). The “mangrove tea” is rich in theaflavin, the substance responsible for the briskness and colour of tea. The tea, which shows no mammalian toxicity, can be improved by UV irradiation (Kathiresan and Pandin, 1991; Kathiresan and Pandin, 1993; Kathiresan, 1995b).

A pyrethrin-like compound in stilt roots of *Rhizophora apiculata* shows strong mosquito larvicidal activity (Thangam, 1990). Smoke from burned extracts repels and kills both *Aedes aegypti* (Thangam and Kathiresan, 1990) and *Culex quinquefasciatus* (Thangam and Kathiresan, 1992b) and extracts applied directly to human skin repel adult *Aedes aegypti* (Thangam and Kathiresan, 1992a).

In aquaculture systems bacterial diseases are responsible for heavy mortalities of cultivable fin fishes and shell fishes. These problems are usually tackled by preventing outbreaks or by treating the actual disease with antimicrobial drugs or antibiotics (Alderman and Michel, 1992). Development of new alternatives,

instead of antibiotics has necessitated because of decreased efficacy and production of resistant strains of pathogens against potent antibiotics (Smith *et al.*, 1994).

All fresh plant materials did also show more antibacterial activity against both bacterial strains than did dried plant extracts. Antibacterial activity of fresh and dried plant materials reduced for both bacterial strains with time after extraction. Since, *L. racemosa* and *A. marina* gave the best inhibition for bacterial species, they were used for further investigations. Charcoal treated plant extracts of *L. racemosa* and *A. marina* were able to inhibit both bacterial strains more than those of untreated plant extracts. Phytochemical screening of mature leaf, bark of *L. racemosa* and leaf extracts of *A. marina* has been carried out and revealed that leaf and bark contained alkaloids, steroids, triterpenoids and flavonoids. None of the above extracts indicate the presence of saponins and cardiac glycosides. Separated bands of extracts by TLC analysis showed antibacterial activity against *S. Aureus* by Abeyasinghe¹ and he also found that the antibacterial activity of the leaves and bark of mangrove plants, *Avicennia marina*, *A. officinalis*, *Bruguiera sexangula*, *Excoecaria agallocha*, *Lumnitzera racemosa* and *Rhizophora apiculata* was evaluated against antibiotic resistant pathogenic bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Proteus sp.*

The antibacterial activity of the mangrove leaves of *Avicennia marina*, *Ceriops decandra* and (non italic) *Bruguiera cylindrica* were tested against antibiotic resistant pathogens (ARB) viz. *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumonia*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and eye pathogens (EP) viz. *E. coli*, *Proteus*, *Acinetobacter* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. Most of the plant extracts showed promising antibacterial activity against both the bacterial groups (Ravikumar, *et al.*, 2011).

The effects of Mangrove extracts on some microorganisms including *Shigella sp.*, *Staphylococcus sp.* and *Pseudomonas sp.* has been reported in some studies in the area of pharmacology. Also different type of solvents including Ethanol, Chloroform and Ethyl acetate have been used for extraction. Different levels of mangrove extract from *Avicenna marina* have been used to consider its antimicrobial effect. A pathogen, gram negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and a rotten fungi, *Penicillium digitatum* has been affected by mangrove extract using disc inhibitory zone (Amirkaveei and Behbahani, 2011).

This status opened a new venue to explore the natural resources i.e. control and/or suppression of bacterial diseases in safe manner. The phytochemical analysis of various mangrove plants indicates the presence of biologically active compounds including tannins, flavonoids, sterols, coumarins, glycosides, fatty acids, organic acids, alkaloids and saponins. Some research represent the antibacterial activity of some mangrove plants against potent bacterial pathogens both aquaculture pathology and human pathological origin are furnished in (Table 1) which is given below,

Mangroves with Antifungal Properties

In vitro antifungal potential of the methanolic extract of bark of seven mangroves was assayed by employing the food poisoning method against plant pathogenic fungi *Alternaria alternata* and *Fusarium moniliforme*. Among these barks the methanol extract of *Agiceras corniculatum* showed maximum inhibition (56%) of *Alternaria alternata* and extract of *Bruguiera gymnorrhiza* exhibited maximum inhibition (57%) of *Fusarium moniliforme* (Powar, *et al.*, 2011).

Fatty acids are widely occurring compounds in natural fats and dietary oils and they are known to have antibacterial and antifungal properties. However, little is known on the antibacterial and antifungal properties of the blind your-eye mangrove (*Excoecaria agallocha*) and this study for the first time determines the fatty acid composition and the antibacterial and antifungal activities of Fatty Acid Methyl Esters (FAME) of the blind- your-eye mangrove plant found along the coastal areas of south India (Agoramoorthy, *et al.*, 2007). *Streptomyces sp.* were isolated from mangrove mud and studied for their ability to produce bioactive metabolites. About 30 percent of the 33 isolates selected indicated antifungal activity against one or more of the fungi tested including *Candida albicans*. The selected isolate,

Table 1: List of mangroves with antibacterial activity (Modified from Premnathan *et al.*, 1999).

S. no.	Mangroves	Most of Susceptible	Moderate susceptible Bacteria
1.	<i>Finlaysonia obovata</i>	<i>Aeromonas hydrophilla</i> , <i>Vibrio alginolyticus</i>	<i>Micrococcus</i> sp, <i>E.coli</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> , <i>staphylococcus aureus</i>
2.	<i>Xylocarpu grananum</i>	<i>Staphylococcus epidermis</i> , <i>S.aureus</i> , <i>Proteus</i> sp, <i>Shigella boyd ii</i> , <i>V. alginolyticus</i>	<i>E.coli</i> , <i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i> , <i>Edwardsiella tarda</i>
3.	<i>Aegiceras corhiculanum</i>	<i>V. alginolyticus</i> , <i>A. hydrophilla</i>	<i>P. eroginosa</i> , <i>P.Fluorescens</i>
4.	<i>Aegialitis rotundifolia</i>	<i>A. hydrophilla</i>	<i>P. fluorescens</i>
5.	<i>Aglaia elliptifolia</i>	<i>V. lgiudyticus</i> , <i>A. hydrophilla</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>E. tarda</i>
6	<i>Cynometra iripa</i>	<i>V. alginolyticus</i> , <i>A. hydrophilla</i>	<i>P. fluorescens</i> , <i>E .tarda</i> , <i>P.aeroginos</i>
7.	<i>Avicennia officinalis</i>	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp
8.	<i>Avicennia marina</i>	<i>Shigella</i> sp, <i>Staphylococcus</i> sp, <i>E. coli</i>	<i>Proteus</i> sp, <i>Pseudomona</i> ssp
9.	<i>Bruguiera sexangula</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Shigella</i> sp <i>Pseudomonas</i> sp
10.	<i>Excoecari agallocha</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> , <i>Micrococcus luteus</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. pumilus</i> , <i>E.coli</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>

Streptomyces strain SS1 had antifungal activity against *C. albicans*, *Fusarium monoliforme*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Pestalotiopsis geupini* and *Pyricularia oryzae* (Vikineswary, *et al.*, 1997).

Mangroves with Antifouling Properties

Marine fouling organisms often cause technical and economic problems by settling on artificial surfaces submerged in seawaters. Although organotin compounds and booster biocides have been widely used for controlling these fouling organisms, they may also pollute the aquatic environments. Along with the increasing concern about environment, effective and environmentally friendly antifoulants are urgently needed. Therefore, an important source of such effective and environmentally friendly antifoulants is based on the research of natural product antifoulants. *Ceriops tagal* Perr. (Rhizophoraceae) is an important mangrove species. This species is rich in terpenoids (including a series of new terpenoids), while marine new terpenoids are an important source of marine antifoulants. . The antifouling activity against larval settlement of the barnacle *Balanus albicostatus* were evaluated using capsaicin as a positive control. All these terpenoids exhibited antifouling activity against cyprid larvae of the barnacle without

significant toxicity (Chen, *et al.*, 2008). And also found that compounds from the roots of *Ceriops tagal* inhibited significantly larval settlement of the barnacle *Balanus albicostatus*, which is one important fouling organism in East Asian coastal waters. These antifouling active compounds included one new diterpene, methoxy-ent-8(14)-pimarenyl-15-one (1) and three known metabolites, designated as ent-8(14)-pimarene-15R, 16- diol (2) and stigmasterol (3) and -sitosterol (4), is shown in (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure of Antifouling compound in *Ceriops tagal*, from Jun De Chen, *et al.*, 2008.

Mangroves with Antiviral Properties

A number of mangroves and associates contain substances which show biological activities such as antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal properties. The study of Premnathan, *et al.*, 1992 and 1996, revealed that the mangroves were found highly effective for antiviral activity as compared to seaweeds and sea grasses. Kokpal *et al.*, 1990, had also reported the bioactive compounds from mangrove plants. Some mangroves had shown insecticidal activity (Miki *et al.*, 1994 and Ishibashi *et al.*, 1993). Wu *et al.*, 1997, reported the cytotoxic and antiplatelet aggregation activity of methanol extract of *Aglaia elliptifolia*. Root, leaf, and stem extracts of *Rhizophora* trees have inhibitory properties against human pathogens like bacteria, viruses and fungi (Hernandez and Perez, 1978), while the polysaccharides derived from the leaves are inhibitors of HIV-1 and SIV, used to treat the early-stage infection of AIDS (Table 2) (Premnathan, *et al.*, 1999).

The bark of *Rhizophora* has been used to cure diabetes and its prop root has been used as a mosquito repellent. The pharmaceutical properties of mangrove trees provide a wide domain for medical use, requiring further studies for possible drug development. Some earlier workers have reported the presence of compounds like tannins, alkaloid and polyphenols in mangroves, which play an important role in the suppression of deleterious microorganisms.

The leaf extracts of *Bruguiera cylindrica* and bark of *Rhizophora mucronata* show antiviral activity against Newcastle disease, Vaccinia and Hepatitis B viruses. Mangroves are widely used by mangrove dwellers for bush medicine e.g. *A. illicifolius* is used for skin disorders, boils and wounds. Numerous medicines derived from mangroves (ashes or bark infusions) can be applied for skin disorders e.g. *Lumnitzera racemosa* and sores including leprosy. They have been reported to treat different kinds of diseases (headaches, boils, ulcers and diarrhoea). Common uses of mangroves in bush medicine are reviewed by Bandaranayake (Bandaranayake, 2002).

Extracts have proven activity against human, animal and plant pathogenic viruses including human immuno-deficiency virus (Premanathan, *et al.*, 1996), Semliki forest virus (Premanathan, *et al.*, 1995), Vaccinia virus, Encephalomyocarditis virus (Premanathan, *et al.*, 1994b), New castle disease virus (Premanathan, *et al.*, 1993) and Hepatitis-B viruses (Premanathan, *et al.*, 1996).

A few mangrove species, particularly those belonging to the family Rhizophoraceae, show particularly strong antiviral activity (Kathiresan, 1995a and Premanathan, *et al.*, 1992). Purified active fractions like acid polysaccharides (galactose, galactosamine, glucose and arabinose) show potent anti-HIV activity (Premanathan, *et al.*, 1999).

In aquaculture systems, viral diseases are of great concern and seven of them are listed by OIE as notifiable due to the intercontinental geographic spread and severe economic losses they incur. A total of 14 species of mangrove plants were found to serve as antiviral herbs against 6 virulent viral pathogens including 4 RNA viruses *viz.*, New castle disease virus (NDV), encephalomyocarditis virus (EMCV), Semliki forest virus (SFV) and human Immunodeficiency syndrome virus (HIV) and two DNA viruses such as Vaccinia virus (VV) and hepatitis B virus (HBV) in *in vitro* study for antibacterial activity (Premanathan, *et al.*, 1999). Out of the fourteen mangrove plants reported, certain mangroves possess antiviral properties against diverse viral pathogens in different disciplines like human pathology, plant pathology and veterinary pathology. This suggests the existence of "Parallel knowledge" in different disciplines with regards to screening of antiviral mangrove plants.

The mode of action of antiviral activity of mangrove plant extract varies with each type of virus. In the case of EMCV, SFV and HIV the antiviral activity is evaluated by the inhibition of cytopathic effect, where as for HBV antiviral activity is evaluated and expressed in terms of percentage of inhibition with the anti HB antibody. For NDV, the antiviral activity of mangrove plant extract was evaluated in terms of percentage of inhibition of haemoagglutination, while in the case of VV the antiviral activity was evaluated by reduction in number of plaques by the mangrove extracts. Moorthy and Kathiresan proposed a physiological grouping of mangrove species based on pigments, which may differ significantly among species (Moorthy and Kathiresan, 1997a). Pigments concentrations may also vary with environmental conditions and season (Bsak, *et al.*, 1998). For example, Menon and Neelakantan found that total chlorophyll content was positively related to light levels (Menon and Neelakanthan, 1992). Oswin and Kathiresan found that mangrove chlorophyll and carotenoid levels, in general are high during the summer but anthocyanin levels are highest in the monsoon months. Flavonoids increased during the premonsoon period (Oswin and Kathiresan, 1997a).

The study was to find out a natural way to fight white spot syndrome virus (WSSV) in cultured shrimps, as the present scenario necessitated an organic remedy for the devastating pathogen in crustaceans. Mangrove extracts screened aqueous extract from *Ceriops tagal* imparted total protection to shrimp from WSSV because this mangrove is having some properties like the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids,

polyphenolics, cardiac glycosides, saponins and sterols founded (Sudheer, *et al.*, 2011).

Table. 2 List of mangroves with antiviral properties (Modified from Smith *et al.*, 1994).

S.no.	Mangrove plant	V i
1.	<i>Acanthus ilicifolius</i>	NDV, HBV
2.	<i>Sesuvium portulacastrum</i>	HBV
3.	<i>Avicennia marina</i>	EMCV, HBV
4.	<i>Avicenia officinalis</i>	VV, EMCV, HIV
5.	<i>Salicornia brachiata</i>	EMCV, HBV
6.	<i>Suaeda monoica</i>	EMCV
7.	<i>Lumnitzera racemosa</i>	NDV, VV, EMCV
8.	<i>Excoecaria agallocha</i>	NDV, EMCV, HIV
9.	<i>Aegiceras corniculatum</i>	NDV, SFV, HBV, HIV
10.	<i>Bruguiera cylindrica</i>	NDV, VV, EMCV, SFV, HBV
11.	<i>Ceriops decandra</i>	VV, SFV, HBV, HIV
12.	<i>Rhizophora apiculata</i>	EMCV, HBV, HIV
13.	<i>Rhizophora lamarckii</i>	EMCV, HBV, SFV, HIV
14.	<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i>	NDV, VV, EMCV, SFV, HBV, HIV

CONCLUSION

In recent years, screening of mangrove plants for a variety of biological activities is gaining importance. Mangroves are biochemically unique, producing a wide array of novel natural products. Mangrove and mangrove associates contain biologically active antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal compounds. Mangrove forests, though essentially common and wide-spread, are highly threatened. Local societies along with their knowledge about the mangrove also are endangered, while they are still underrepresented as scientific research topics. So there is a great need to conserve the mangrove forests.

With this literature we have tried to give some knowledge on the utilization patterns, and mangrove plants with broad spectrum medicinal and antimicrobial activity, which could be fused together to arrive at an innovative compounds for tackling virulent and dreadful viral and bacterial pathogen. Care must be taken in the development of such innovative compounds are ecologically safe and economically viable by performing a role in protection from emerging diseases and also prevent the risk of development of resistant strains of pathogens.

REFERENCES

- Abeyasinghe (2010): Antibacterial activity of some medicinal mangroves against antibiotic resistant pathogenic bacteria. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical science*, 72(2), 167-172.
- Achmadi, S., Syahbirin, G., Choong, E. T. and Hemingway, R. W. (1994): Catechin-3-O-rhamnoside chain extender units in polymeric procyanidins from mangrove bark. *Phytochemistry*, 35(1), 217-219.
- Agoramoorthy, G., Chandrasekarau, V., Vemkatesalu, V. and Hsu, M. J. (2007): Antibacterial and antifungal activity of fatty acid methyl esters of blind-your-eye mangrove from India. *Braz. J. Microbiol.*, 38, 739-742.
- Alderman, D. J. and Michel, C. (1992): Chemotherapy in aqua culture today from theory to reality Office. *Int. Des. Epizooties Paris.*, 293, 4.
- Bandaranayake, W. M. (1998): Traditional and medicinal uses of mangroves. *Mangroves and Salt Marshes*, 2, 133-148.
- Bandaranayake, W. M. (2002): Bioactivities, bioactive compounds and chemical constituents of mangrove plants. *Wetlands Ecology and Management*, 10, 421-452.
- Basak, U. C., Das, A. B. and Das, P. (1998): Seasonal changes in organic constituents in leaves of nine mangrove species. *Marine and Freshwater Research*, 49(5), 369-372.
- Benner, R., Weliky, K. and Hedges, J. I. (1990a): Early diagnosis of mangrove leaves in a tropical estuary; molecular-level analyses of neutral sugars and lignin-derived phenols. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta.*, 54(7), 1991-2001.
- Chapman, V. J. (1970): Mangrove phytosociology. *Tropical Ecology*, 11, 1-1.
- Chelliah, S. (2001): Mangrove Forests: A Threatened Ecosystem. *Yojana*, 45, 30-31.
- Conti, E., Litt, A. and Sytsma, K. J. (1996): Circumscription of myrtales and their relationships to other rosids: evidence from rbcL sequence data. *American Journal of Botany*, 83, 221-233.
- Dodd, R. S., Fromard, F., Rafii, Z. A. and Blasco, F. (1995): Biodiversity among West African, Rhizophora: Foliar wax chemistry. *Biochemical Systematics and Ecology*, 23(7-8), 859-868.
- Duke, N. C. (1992): Tropical Mangrove Ecosystems. In *Coastal and Estuarine studies* (ed. Robertson, A.I. and Alongi, D.M.), American Geophysical Union, Washington DC, USA, pp. 63-100.
- Han, W. D., Chen, L. and Yuan, M. J. (2004): The barnacle control on the planted young mangle trees. *J. Fujian Forestry Sci. Tech.*, 31(1), 57-70.
- Ishibashi, F., Satasook, C., Isman, M. B. And Towers, G. H. N. (1993): Insecticidal 1H-Cyclopentatetrahydro [b] Benzofurans from *Aglaia odorata*. *Phytochemistry*, 32, 307-310.

Jun De Chen, Dan Qin Feng , Zhi Wei Yang , Zhan Chang Wang , Yan Qiu and Yi Ming Lin (2008): Antifouling Metabolites from the Mangrove Plant *Ceriops tagal*. *Molecules*, 13, 212-219.

Kathiresan, K. and Ravi, V. (1990): Seasonal changes in tannin content of mangrove leaves. *The Indian Forester*, 116(5), 390-392.

Kathiresan, K. (1995a): *Rhizophora annamalayana*: A new species of mangrove. *Environment and Ecology*, 13(1), 240-241.

Kathiresan, K. (2000): A review of studies on Pichavaram mangrove, Southeast India. *Hydrobiologia*, 430(1), 185-205.

Kathiresan, K., Moorthy, P. and Ravikumar, S. (1995): Studies on root growth in seedlings of a tropical mangrove tree species. *International Tree Crops Journal*, 8(2-3), 183-188.

Kathiresan, K. and Pandian, M. (1991): Effect of UV on quality of black tea from *Ceriops decandra*. *Science and Culture*, 57(3), 93-95.

Kathiresan, K. and Pandin, M. (1993): Effect of UV on black tea constituents of mangrove leaves. *Science and Culture*, 59, 61-63.

Kathiresan, K., Thangam, T. S., and Premanathan, M. (1995a): Mangrove halophytes: potential source of medicines. In *Biology of Salt Tolerant Plants* (ed. M. A. Khan, I.A. Ungar), University of Karachi, Pakistan, pp. 361-370.

Kathiresan, K. and Thangam, T. S. (1987): Biototoxicity of *Excoecaria agallocha* latex on marine organisms. *Current Science*, 56(7), 314-315.

Kathiresan, K. and Thangam, T. S. (1989): Effect of leacates from mangrove leaf on rooting of *Rhizophora* seedlings. *Geobios*, 16(1), 27-29.

Kathiresan, K. (1995b): Studies on tea from mangrove leaves. *Environment and Ecology*, 13(2), 321-323.

Kokpal, V., Miles, D. H., Payne, A. M. and Chittawong, V. (1990): Chemical constituents and bioactive compounds from mangrove plants. *Studies in Natural Products Chemistry*, 7, 175-199.

Macnae, W. (1968): A general account of the fauna and flora of mangrove swamps and forests in the Indo-West-Pacific region. *Adv. Mar. Biol.*, 6, 73-270.

Menon, G. G. and Neelakanthan, B. (1992): Chlorophyll and Light attenuation from the leaves of mangroves species of kali estuary. *Indian journal of marine science*, 21(1): 13-16.

Miki, T., Sakaki, T., Shibata, M., Inukai, Y., Hirosue, H., Ikema, Y. and Yaga, S. (1994): Soxhlet extraction of mangrove and biological activities of extracts. *Kyushu Kogyo Gijutsu Kenkyusho Hokoku*, 53, 3347-3352.

Mishra, B. K. et al. (2009): Social issues and concerns in biodiversity conservation: experiences from wildlife protected areas in India. *Tropical Ecology*, 50, 147-1.

Moor thy, E. (1995): Effects of UV-B radiation on mangrove environment: Physiological responses of *Rhizophora apiculata* Blume. *Ph. D. thesis*, Annamalai University, India, pp. 130.

Moorthy, P. and Kathiresan, K. (1997a): Photosynthetic pigments in tropical mangroves: Impacts of

seasonal flux on UV B radiation and other environmental attributes. *Botanica Marina*, 40, 341-349.

Oswin, S. D. and Kathiresan, K. (1994): Pigments in mangrove species of Pichavaram. *Indian Journal of Marine Sciences*, 23(1), 64-66.

Phongboonrod, S. and Mai Thed Mueong Thai. (1976): *Folkloric Use of Thai and Foreign medicinal plants*. Bangkok, Chiwat Press Co.

Powar, P. S., Chavan, S. R. and Gaikwad, D. K. (2011): Antifungal activity of mangrove bark. *International Journal of Pharma and Bio Science*, 2, 4.

Premanathan, M., Kathiresan, K. and Chandra, K. (1994b): Anti-viral activity of marine and coastal plants from India. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy*, 32, 330-336.

Premanathan, M., Arakaki, R., Izumi, H., Kathiresan, K., Nakano, M., Yamamoto, N. and Nakashima, H. (1999): Antiviral properties of a mangrove plant, *Rhizophora apiculata* Blume, against Human Immunodeficiency Virus. *Antiviral Res.*, 44, 113-122.

Premanathan, M., Kathiresan, K. and Chandra, K. (1995): Antiviral evaluation of some marine plants against Semliki forest virus. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy*, 33(1), 75-77.

Premanathan, M., Kathiresan, K., Chandra, K. and Bajpai, S. K. (1993): Antiviral activity of marine plants against Newcastle Disease Virus. *Tropical Biomedicine*, 10, 31-33.

Premanathan, M., Kathiresan, K. and Nakashima, H. (1999): Mangrove halophytes a source of antiviral substances. *South Pacific Study*, 19(1-2), 49-57.

Premanathan, M., Nakashima, H., Kathiresan, K., Rajendran, N. and Yamamoto, N. (1996): In-vitro anti-human immunodeficiency virus activity of mangrove plants. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 130, 276-279.

Premanathan, M., Chandra, K., Bajpai, S. K. and Kathiresan, K. (1992): A survey of some Indian marine plants for antiviral activity. *Botanica Marina*, 35, 321-324.

Premanathan, M., Nakashima, H., Kathiresan, K., Rajendran, N. and Yamamoto, N. (1996): In-vitro anti-human immunodeficiency virus activity of mangrove plants. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 103, 278-281.

Ravikumar, S., Jacob Inbaneson, S., Uthira Selvam, M., Kaleeswari, R., Ramu, A. and Margaret Beula, B. (2011): Antibacterial Activity of Heterotrophic Endophytes from Karangakadu Mangrove Ecosystem. *India. J. Pharm. Res.*, 4(1), 195-198.

Rojas Hernandez, N. M. and Coto Perez, O. (1978): Antimicrobial properties of extracts from *Rhizophora* mangrove. *L. Rev Cubana Med Trop.*, 30, 181-187.

Shiva Amirkaveei and Behrouz Alizadeh Behbahani (2011): *International Conference on Food Engineering and Biotechnology*. Singapore: IPCBEE, 9.

Smith, T. J. III., Robblee, M. B., Wanless, H. R. and Doyle, T. W. (1994): Mangroves, hurricanes, and lightning strikes: Assessment of Hurricane Andrew suggests an interaction across two differing scales of disturbance. *Bioscience*, 44(4), 256-262.

Sudheer, N. S., Rosamma Philip, I. S. and Bright Singh (2011): In vivo screening of mangrove plants for anti WSSV activity in *Penaeus monodon*, and evaluation of *Cerriops tagal* as a potential source of antiviral molecules. *Aquaculture*, (In Press), DOI Information: doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture. 2010.11.016.

Sujamngong, P. (1979): Folkloric medicine, herbal medicines and traditional medicines in Thailand. In *Thai-Chinese medical text book*, Praewitaya Press, Bangkok.

Thangam, T. S. and Katiresan, K. (1992a): Mosquito larvicidal activity of mangrove plant extract against *Aedes aegypti*. *International Pest Control*, 34(4), 116-119.

Thangam, T. S. (1990): Studies on marine plants for mosquito control. *Ph. D. Thesis*, Annamalai University, India, pp. 68.

Thangam, T. S. and Kathiresan, K. (1992b): Smoke repellency and killing effect of marine plants against *Culex quinquefasciatus*. *Tropical Biomedicine*, 9, 35-38.

Thangam, T. S. and Kathiresan, K. (1991): Mosquito larvicidal activity of marine plant extracts with synthetic insecticides. *Botanica Marina*, 34(6), 537-539.

Thangam, T. S. and Kathiresan, K. (1994): Mosquito larvicidal activity of *Rhizophora apiculata* Blume. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy*, 32, 33-36.

Thangam, T. S. and Kathiresan, K. (1997): Mosquito larvicidal activity of mangrove plant extracts and synergistic activity of *Rhizophora apiculata* with pyrethrum against *Culex quinquefasciatus*. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy*, 35, 1-3.

Tomlinson, P. B. (1986): *The Botany of mangroves*, Cambridge University Press. Cambridge, U. K., pp. 413.

Vikineswary, S., Nadaraj, P., Wong, W. H. and Balabaskaran, S. (1997): Actinomycetes from a tropical mangrove ecosystem Antifungal activity of selected strains. *Asia Pacific J. Mol. Biol. Boitec.*, 5(2), 81-86.

Walsh, G. E. (1974): Mangrove: a review. In: Acad. Press. Inc., *Ecology of halophytes*. New York.

Wu, T. S., Liou, M. J., Kuon, C. S., Teng, C. M., Nagao, T. and Lee, K. W. (1997): Cytotoxic and antiplatelet aggregation principles from *Aglaia elliptifolia*. *Journal of Natural Products*, 60, 606-608.

Yaadfon Association (1981): *Use of medicinal plants in mangrove forest*. Green Group, Trang.

Received for Publication: 17/02/2012

Accepted for Publication: 22/03/2012

Corresponding author

Vijay Kumar Reddy, S,

Department of Fish Processing Technology, College of Fisheries, Mangalore, Karnataka, India – 575 001,

E-mail: bhajarangbhali@gmail.com